

THE
PHILODROMIDAE
OF
SOUTH AFRICA

Compiled by: A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman, C.R. Haddad, S.H. Foord, L.N. Lotz

South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide Philodromidae 2021 version 1: 1-52

THE PHILODROMIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

Dippenaar-Schoeman, A.S.^{1,2}, Haddad, C.R.³, Foord, S.H.², & Lotz, L.N.⁴ 2021. *South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: The Philodromidae of South Africa*. 2021 version 1: 1-52

¹ARC-Plant Health and Protection, Private Bag X134, Queenswood, Pretoria, 0121, South Africa

²Department of Zoology, University of Venda, Private Bag X5050, Thohoyandou, 0950, South Africa

³Department of Zoology and Entomology, University of the Free State, P.O. Box 339, Bloemfontein, 9300, South Africa

⁴National Museum, Bloemfontein, P.O. Box 266, Bloemfontein, 9300, South Africa

ABSTRACT

The Philodromidae are represented by 30 genera, eight are known from the Afrotropical Region and six from South Africa where it is represented by 34 species. Only one genus *Tibellus* has been revised. Most of the genera of the Philodromidae are very commonly sampled from plants with only a few genera and species found living on the ground. During SANSa surveys >2243 accessions were deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida but of these accessions 46% were not identified to species level. Of the 34 species presently recorded from South Africa, 30 have a wide distribution and is listed of Least Concern with only three *Philodromus* species and a single *Thanatus* that are data deficient.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) and the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) Threatened Species Programme; the Universities of the Free State, Venda and Pretoria; the National Research Foundation (NRF) for generously funding and support. The staff of the Arachnology section at the National Collection of Arachnida (Connie Anderson, Petro Marais, Sma Mathebula, Robin Lyle and Annette van den Berg), as well as several volunteers from the public, are thanked for their assistance with the sorting and databasing of specimens collected during the SANSa surveys. Various students, members of the public and the Spider Club of Southern Africa collected material for SANSa. We also thank the South African National Parks and E. Oppenheimer & Son for support and providing opportunity to collect in the parks and reserves as well as the provincial conservation agencies for collecting permits. We are especially thankful to all the photographers who provided photographs for the SANSa Virtual Museum without their contribution this guide would have not been possible.

CONTENTS

FAMILY PHILODROMIDAE Thorell, 1870	4
GENUS GEPHYROTA Strand, 1932	5
• <i>Gephyrota glauca</i> (Jézéquel, 1966)	6-7*
GENUS HIRRIUSA Strand, 1932	8
• <i>Hirriusa arenacea</i> (Lawrence, 1927)	9-10*
• <i>Hirriusa bidentata</i> (Lawrence, 1927)	11*
• <i>Hirriusa variegata</i> (Simon, 1895) ..	12
GENUS PHILODROMUS Walckenaer, 1826	13
• <i>Philodromus bigibbus australis</i> Lawrence, 1928	14
• <i>Philodromus brachycephalus</i> Lawrence, 1952	15
• <i>Philodromus browningi</i> Lawrence, 1952 ..	16
• <i>Philodromus epigynatus</i> Strand, 1909	17
• <i>Philodromus grosi</i> Lessert, 1943	18*
• <i>Philodromus guineensis</i> Millot, 1941	19*
• <i>Philodromus partitus</i> Lessert, 1919	20*
• <i>Philodromus thanatellus</i> Strand, 1909	21
• <i>Philodromus vulpio</i> Simon, 1910	22
GENUS SUEMUS Simon, 1895	23
• <i>Suemus punctatus</i> Lawrence, 1938	24
GENUS THANATUS C. L. Koch, 1837	25
• <i>Thanatus africanus</i> Karsch, 1878	26
• <i>Thanatus atlanticus</i> Berland, 1936.....	27*
• <i>Thanatus dorsilineatus</i> Jézéquel, 1964.....	28*
• <i>Thanatus fabricii</i> (Audouin, 1826)	29*
• <i>Thanatus lamottei</i> Jézéquel, 1964	30*
• <i>Thanatus namaquensis</i> Simon, 1910	31
• <i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	32-33*
GENUS TIBELLUS Simon, 1875	34
• <i>Tibellus armatus</i> Lessert, 1928	35
• <i>Tibellus australis</i> (Simon, 1910)	36*
• <i>Tibellus bruneitarsis</i> Lawrence, 1952	37
• <i>Tibellus cobusi</i> Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994	38
• <i>Tibellus demangei</i> Jézéquel, 1964	39
• <i>Tibellus flavipes</i> Caporiacco, 1939	40
• <i>Tibellus gerhardi</i> Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994	41
• <i>Tibellus hollidayi</i> Lawrence, 1952	42-43
• <i>Tibellus kibonotensis</i> Lessert, 1919	44
• <i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	45-46
• <i>Tibellus seriepunctatus</i> Simon, 1907	47
• <i>Tibellus sunetae</i> Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994	48
• <i>Tibellus vossioni</i> Simon, 1884	49
UNDETERMINED SPECIES	50
REFERENCES	51-52

* Not listed in the World Spider Catalog 2021 for South Africa

FAMILY PHILODROMIDAE Thorell, 1870

The Philodromidae are represented by 30 genera, eight of which occur in the Afrotropical Region and six in South Africa known from 34 species (World Spider Catalog 2021).

COMMON NAME: Running spiders.

MORPHOLOGY: Small to medium-sized (3-16 mm). Colour varies from white to pale cream and reddish brown or greyish brown; frequently mottled, with longitudinal bands or chevrons. Carapace slightly flattened; clothed in soft recumbent setae; shape varies from as long as wide to elongated; eyes eight; in two rows (4:4); eyes usually equal in size; not on tubercles; both eye rows recurved; secondary eyes lack a tapetum; cheliceral furrow usually without teeth. Abdomen variable in shape, from heart-shaped to oval or elongated; covered with soft recumbent setae; usually with dark, heart-shaped mark; spinnerets simple. Legs laterigrade and slender; legs I, III and IV almost equal in length, leg II usually longer, sometimes much longer than rest of legs; tarsi with two claws; tarsi I and II with claw tufts and scapulae.

LIFE STYLE: Philodromids are free-living hunters and most of the genera are commonly found on plants with only a few genera and species found living on the ground. Their movements are erratic and using their claw tufts and scopulae, they are able to move about swiftly. Their laterigrade legs and flat bodies enable them to hide in crevices (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014)

TAXONOMY: Of the six genera known from South Africa only *Tibellus* has been revised (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman 1994).

Philodromidae. a: *Tibellus* sp., female, dorsal view; b: *Philodromus* sp., female, dorsal view; c: spinnerets, ventral view; d: male palp, ventral view; e: male palp, lateral view; f: epigyne (After Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué 1997).

GENUS *GEPHYROTA* Strand, 1932

The genus *Gephyrota* described by Strand (1932) is represented by seven species (World Spider Catalog 2021) and two are known from Africa and one from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: White Running Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Gephyra limbata* L. Koch, 1875

MORPHOLOGY: *Gephyrota* is a small genus of philodromids that are pale in colour, lightly covered with short setae. Carapace round, slightly flattened and wider than long; slightly narrower in the eye region; eyes are in two rows; both rows recurved; eyes the same size. Abdomen oval but pointed towards the spinnerets; white sometimes with scattered dark markings. Legs are almost the same length with only leg II slightly longer.

LIFESTYLE: Free living plant dweller. Specimens are frequently sampled sweeping the vegetation.

TAXONOMY: No species have yet been described from South Africa.

Gephyrota glauca female eye pattern Photo Peter Webb

Gephyrota glauca female Photo Peter Webb

Gephyrota glauca (Jézéquel, 1966)

COMMON NAME: White Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Jézéquel (1966) as *Gephyra glauca* from Ivory Coast. It is recorded from several African countries. In South Africa sampled from eight provinces including >10 protected areas (EOO= 819 893 km²; AOO= 108 km²; 4-1730m a.s.l.). Due to the wide range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free living plant dwellers that are commonly found in sweep net samples. Sampled from Fynbos, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). Also from crops such as macadamia, maize, pistachio, sunflower and tomatoes (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Cameroon, Ivory Coast, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); East London (-33.01, 27.9); Ongeluksnek (-30.55, 28.57); East London (Pineapple Research Station) (-33.01, 27.9). **Free State:** Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-29.518, 25.268); Wyndford Guest Farm, Fouriesburg (-28.7, 28.24); Amanzi Nature Reserve (-28.62, 26.68). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/ Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve, Bronkhortspruit (-25.700, 28.941). **Kwa-Zulu-Natal:** Cathedral Peak (-28.94, 29.19); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Hell's Gate (-28, 32.48); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83); Good Hope Plantation, Boston Midlands (-29.651, 29.976). **Limpopo:** Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16). **Mpumalanga:** Blyde River Canyon Nature Reserve (-24.58, 30.82). **Northern Cape:** Nieuwoudtville (-31.37, 19.11); Prieska (-29.68, 22.74); Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.561, 24.162); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44). **Western Cape:** Bloubergstrand (-33.77, 18.45); Cape Agulhas (-34.81, 19.81); Cederberg Wilderness Area (-32.16, 18.89); Fisherhaven, Hermanus District (-34.47, 19.27); Paarl (-33.71, 18.98); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Yzerfontein (-33.34, 18.16); Robben Island (-33.80, 18.35); Fernkloof Nature Reserve Hermanus (-34.61, 19.34); Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve (-34.32, 18.96); Bloubergstrand (-33.77, 18.45); Uitzicht Annex Knysna (-34.00, 23.20)

Gephyrota glauca female Photo Wolf Avni

Gephyrota glauca female Photo Clarissa de Lange

Epigynum and palp after Jézéquel (1966)

Gephyrota glauca (continued)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in >10 protected areas such as the Blouberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2019), Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009), Tswalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018) and Amanzi Nature Reserve (Haddad & Butler 2018). No conservation actions are required.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Gephyrota glauca female Photo Vida vd Walt

Gephyrota glauca female Photo Allen Jones

GENUS *HIRRIUSA* Strand, 1932

The genus *Hirriusa* was described by Strand (1932) and is known from three species recorded only from South Africa and Namibia (World Spider Catalog 2021).

COMMON NAME: Ground running spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Hirriusa variegata* (Simon, 1895).

MORPHOLOGY: Both sexes medium-sized. Colour cryptic usually creamish brown with darker patterns with legs banded. Carapace slightly flattened; as wide as long; suboval in outline; thoracic region evenly rounded, sloping gently towards cephalic region; fovea usually distinct; integument covered with short setae; genus can be recognised by the recurved anterior eye row; anterior eyes the same size, larger than the eyes of the posterior eye row. Abdomen oval; with a light cover of short setae; heart-shaped mark usually visible. Legs slender and long; arranged sideways.

LIFESTYLE: Small ground-running spiders frequently encountered in sandy regions. With their cryptic colouration, they are well camouflaged and not easily seen on the soil surface. They are agile and are readily collected in pitfall traps. They have frequently been encountered in areas infested with harvester termites. They readily feed on them in the laboratory and may be an important predator of these insects. The egg-sac is covered with sand and deposited under stones or debris on the ground.

TAXONOMY: Not revised.

Hirriusa eye pattern dorsal view

Hirriusa eye pattern anterior view

Hirriusa arencea Photo Peter Webb

Hirriusa bidentatus Photo Peter Webb

Hirriusa variegata Photo Peter Webb

Hirriusa sp. with egg sac Photo L. Oates

Hirriusa arenacea (Lawrence, 1927)

COMMON NAME: Namibia Ground Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African spider described by Lawrence (1927) as *Hirrius arenaceus* from Namibia. It is recorded from three African countries. In South Africa known from seven provinces including seven protected areas (EOO= 993 385 km²; AOO= 116 km²; 377-1513 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: A free-living agile ground dweller readily collected in pitfall traps. With their cryptic colouration, they are well camouflaged and not easily seen on the soil surface. They are frequently encountered in areas infested with termites. Sampled from the Grassland, Desert, Nama Karoo, Savanna, Succulent Karoo and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2011). It is also recorded from pistachio orchards (Haddad et al. 2004; Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, Botswana, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Cradock (-32.10, 25.37). **Free State:** Luckhoff, Farm Bankfontein-Nama Karoo veld (-30.063, 24.897); Golden Gate Highlands NP (-28.31, 28.37); Bloemfontein (-29.08, 26.10); Qwa Qwa Nature Reserve, Spelonken (-28.28, 28.38); Allemanskraal Dam (-28.17, 27.10); Pinekloof (-29.14, 27.24); Groenhoek (Berghut) (-30.16, 27.13). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Hlabisa, Mondumysa (-28.15, 31.87). **Limpopo:** Ndengeza (-23.316, 30.4114); Vyeboom (-23.1439, 30.3797); Goro Game Ranch near Vivo (-22.99, 29.43); Limpopo Valley, farm Stoke (-22.476, 29.870). **Northern Cape:** Riemvasmaak (-28.53, 20.29); 4 km W of Hopetown (-29.62, 24.06); Klein Papkuil farm (-28.48, 23.72); Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76); Prieska, Green Valley Nuts Estate (-29.68, 22.74); Prieska (Farm Remhoogte) (-29.52, 23); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17); Strydenburg, between Britstown and Hopetown (-29.95, 23.68); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44); Benfontein, Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82). **North West:** Stella 30.5 km N (-26.29, 24.78). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West from following farms: Farm 151b (-32.32, 22.44); Farm Alexanderskraal (-32.58, 22.71); Farm Bokvlei (-32.43, 22.35); Farm De Pannen (-32.61, 23.10); Farm Eerste Water (-32.61; 23.10); Farm Groot Kraanvogelfontein (-32.92, 22.64); Farm Juriesfontein (-32.53, 23.43); Farm Kantkraal (-33.28, 23.22); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Aardvark Nature Reserve (-33.494, 21.088).

Palp after Lawrence(1927).

Epigynum after Lawrence(1927).

Hirriusa arenacea female from Aardvark NR Photo Peter Webb

Hirriusa arenacea (continued)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in several protected areas such as Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020); Mountain Zebra National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2006); Golden Gate Highlands National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020); Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999); Tswalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Hirriusa arenacea female from Aardvark NR Photo Peter Webb

Hirriusa bidentata (Lawrence, 1927)

COMMON NAME: Northern Cape Ground Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African spider described by Lawrence (1927) as *Hirrius bidentatus* from Namibia. The species is known from two African countries. In South Africa recorded from four provinces including two protected areas (EOO=277 792 km²; AOO= 36 km²; 78-1587 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free living ground dwellers. They were sampled from pitfall traps and are frequently associated with termites. Sampled from the Grassland, Fynbos, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Luckhoff (-29.73, 24.77). **Limpopo:** Makgabeng area, W of Senwabawana (Bochum) (-23.24, 28.85); Limpopo Valley farm Stoke (-22.492, 29.881); Rochdale farm (-22.54, 29.41); Lephahlale (-23.48, 27.46). **Northern Cape:** 4 km W of Hopetown (-29.62, 24.06); Kuruman, 22 km S, Farm Mansfield (-27.71, 23.42). **Western Cape:** Gamkaberg Nature Reserve (-33.31, 21.71); Mamre (-33.5, 18.45); Cederberg Wilderness Area (-32.16, 18.89); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sawadee 344 m a.s.l. (-32.34, 18.99); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop (-32.35, 19.17).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Gamkaberg Nature Reserve and in several localities in the Cederberg Wilderness Area. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Palp and epigynum after Lawrence (1927)

Hirriusa bidentatus female from Lephahlale Photo Peter Webb

Hirriusa bidentatus female Photo ASD

Hirriusa variegata (Simon, 1895)

COMMON NAME: Banded Leg Ground Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African spider described by Simon (1895) as *Hirrius variegatus* from the type locality only listed as Transvaal. The species has a wide distribution and has been recorded from five provinces including eight protected areas (EOO= 746 051 km²; AOO= 100 km²; 172-1828 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide range therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: A free running ground dweller frequently sampled from pitfall traps. They have been associated with termites. Sampled from the Grassland, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Nooitgedacht farm, Krugersdorp (-25.86, 27.52). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Waterpoort, N slopes of Soutpansberg (-22.54, 29.37); Limpopo Valley farm Stoke (-22.492, 29.881); Goro Game Ranch, near Vivo (-22.99, 29.43); Vhembe Biosphere, Barries Farm (-22.473, 29.408); Vhembe Biosphere, Bristow Farm (-23.176, 29.764); Waterpoort (-22.54, 29.37); Lephalale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71); Turfloop (-23.88, 29.73). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (-24.98, 31.58); Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-25, 31.97); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Kruger National Park Lwakahle 08 (-25.43, 31.75). **Northern Cape:** Klein Papkuil Farm (-28.48, 23.72); Suffolk Farm nr Hopetown (-29.58, 24.24); Namaqua National Park (-30.05, 17.35); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44); Jakkalswater 3 km from Nababeep (-29.37, 17.48). **Western Cape:** Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Beaufort West (-33.28, 23.22); Matjiesfontein (-33.24, 20.58).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in eight protected areas. Blouberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2019); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009) and the Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020). More sampling needed to collect male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from female.

Hirriusa variegata female van Jakkalsdaraai Photo Peter Webb

Hirriusa variegata male Photo ASD

Hirriusa variegata female Photo Les Oates

Palp undescribed male Photo ASD

GENUS *PHILODROMUS* Walckenaer, 1826

Philodromus is a large genus represented by 207 species and six subspecies distributed worldwide. Thirty-two species are known from the Afrotropical Region and ten are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2021).

COMMON NAME: Philodromus Running spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Philodromus aureolus* (Clerck, 1757)

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: 3–8 mm, males and females similar in size. Colour: varies from white or cream to reddish brown to greyish brown, frequently with a mottled appearance or longitudinal stripes or chevrons on the abdomen; carapace slightly flattened and clothed with soft recumbent setae, shape varying from as long as wide to elongate; eyes: eight in two rows, usually equal in size; both eye rows recurved; posterior median eyes are approximately as far from the posterior lateral eyes as from each other or closer to each other than the posterior lateral eyes. The anterior median eyes are approximately equal in diameter to the anterior lateral eyes.

LIFESTYLE: *Philodromus* occur on tree trunks, in low bushes and on herbage and have been collected from a variety of endemic trees throughout South Africa. *Philodromus* spp., which are grey to brownish yellow, move about rapidly on plants, usually capturing prey by lying in ambush with legs extended. They may play an important role in apple orchards as predators of injurious insects or mites.

TAXONOMY: Not revised and is represented by several undescribed species.

Philodromus sp. carapace

Philodromus sp. Photo Peter Webb

Philodromus sp. Photo Peter Webb

Philodromus bigibbus australis Lawrence, 1928

COMMON NAME: Shouldered Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A subspecies of *Philodromus bigibbus* a species, which has a very wide distribution recorded from Africa, India and Arabia. *Philodromus bigibbus australis* described from South Africa is recorded from five provinces including six protected areas (EOO= 351 431 km²; AOO= 36 km²; 206-1649 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide range listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: They are free-living plant dwellers sampled from vegetation. Sampled from the Grassland, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al 2011; Haddad et al. 2013)

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Alexandria (-33.65, 26.4). **Gauteng:** Kempton Park (-26.09, 28.23); Johannesburg (-26.2, 28.04); Roodeplaat (Farm Leeufontein) (-25.63, 28.34). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Venetia, Limpopo Valley Reserve (-22.320, 29.324); Marakele National Park (-24.41, 27.64). **North West:** Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Northern Cape:** Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Protected in six protected areas. Blouberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2019), Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009) and Tswalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018). More sampling needed to collect male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from female.

Philodromus bigibbus australis Photo Peter Webb

Epigynum after Lawrence (1928)

Eye pattern Photo ASD

Philodromus bigibbus australis from Johannesburg
Photo Renata Kruyswijk

Philodromus brachycephalus Lawrence, 1952

COMMON NAME: Spotted Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1952 from Pietermaritzburg in South Africa and also sampled from Tanzania. In South Africa known from four provinces including six protected areas (EOO= 418 422 km²; AOO= 64 km²; 48-1730 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: They are free-living plant dwellers sampled from vegetation. Species sampled from the Grassland, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). The species was also sampled from avocado and macadamia orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Tanzania and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Fort Brown Kudu Reserve (-33.13, 26.62); Great Fish River Wetland Park, at boundary of Farm Bucklands (-33.48, 27.13); Addo National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Jeffreys Bay (-34.048, 24.92). **Free State:** National Botanical Gardens, Bloemfontein (-29.05, 26.21). **Gauteng:** Kliprivier Nature Reserve (-26.18, 28.00); Tswaing crater Nature reserve (-25.41, 28.08); Faerie Glen Nature Reserve (-25.771, 28.301). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38). **Limpopo:** University of Limpopo, Sovenga Hill (-23.88, 29.73); Lephahlale, farm Zandrivier (-23.48, 27.46); Venetia, Limpopo Valley Reserve (-22.320, 29.324); Goro Game Ranch near Vivo (-22.99, 29.43). **Mpumalanga:** Nelspruit, ARC-ITSC (-25.47, 30.96); 15 km NW of Schagen (-25.43, 30.8); Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Protected in six protected areas. More sampling needed to collect male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from female.

Epigynum after Lawrence (1952)

Epigynum Photo CH

Philodromus brachycephalus Photo C. Haddad

Philodromus brachycephalus Photo P. Webb

Philodromus browningi Lawrence, 1952

COMMON NAME: Banded Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1952 from Pietermaritzburg. The species has also been sampled from Zimbabwe and Swaziland. In South Africa known from seven provinces including >10 protected areas (EOO= 929 734 km²; AOO= 136 km²; 19-1730 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide range therefore listed as of being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: They are free-living plant dwellers sampled from vegetation. Sampled from all the biomes except Desert and Succulent Karoo (Foord et al 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). It was also found in pecan and pistachio orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe, Swaziland, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mazeppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Silaka Nature Reserve (-31.62, 29.49); Cradock (-32.10, 25.37); Mountain Zebra NP (-32.15, 25.27). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Bloemfontein Botanical gardens (-29.11, 26.22); Golden Gate Highlands NP (-28.31, 28.37); Bloemfontein (-29.08, 26.10); Qwa Qwa Nat Res, Spelonken (-28.28, 28.38); Allemanskraal Dam (-28.17, 27.10); Pinekloof (-29.14, 27.24); Groenhoek (Berghut) (-30.16, 27.13). **Gauteng:** Irene (-25.868, 28.218); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.80, 28.77); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Entabeni Forest (-23.00, 30.23); Kruger National Park (Shingwedzi, 20km SE) (-23.22, 31.56); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Marakele National Park (-24.41, 27.64). **Northern Cape:** Schmidtsdrif (-28.7, 24.05); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44); Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.561, 24.162). **Western Cape:** Fernkloof Nature Reserve (-34.86, 19.34); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Worcester (-33.64, 19.47).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Protected in >10 protected areas But more sampling needed to collect the male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from female.

Epigynum after Lawrence (1952)

Epigynum Photo CH

Carapace Photo ASD

Philodromus browningi female Photo Charles Haddad

Philodromus browningi female from Kalkfontein-dam Nature Reserve Photo N. Josling

Philodromus epigynatus Strand, 1909

COMMON NAME: Simonstown Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described in 1909 and known only from the type locality Simonstown (EOO= 4 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 125 m a.s.l.). Type specimen was lost during the Second World War. Too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: They are free-living plant dwellers sampled from vegetation. Sampled from the Fynbos Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Simonstown (Millers point) (-34.19, 18.42).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Last sampled in 1909, more sampling needed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from female.

Philodromus epigynatus female dorsal and ventral view from Robben Island Photo ASD

Philodromus grosi Lessert, 1943

COMMON NAME: Oval Bodied Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1943 from the Congo Republic. It has also been recorded from South Africa from five provinces including >10 protected areas (EOO= 459 149 km²; AOO= 100 km²; 59-1909 m a.s.l.). This species is however under collected and suspected to occur in the countries in-between. Due to wide range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: They are free-living plant dwellers sampled from soil surface from the Fynbos, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Congo, Zimbabwe, Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Clocolan, Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58); Wyndford Guest Farm, Fouriesburg (-28.7, 28.24); Golden Gate Highlands NP (-28.31, 28.37); Bloemfontein (-29.08, 26.10); Farm Opnek (-30.16, 27.13); Bloemfontein Botanical Gardens (-29.08, 26.10); Tussen die Riviere Nat Res (-30.29, 26.07); Amanzi Private Game Res (-28.36, 26.26); Scotland farm (-27.59, 29.37). **Gauteng:** Irene Veld field opposite Gem Village (-25.868, 28.218); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.80, 28.77); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08); Serene Valley, Pretoria (-25.797, 28.298); Alice Glockner Nature Reserve, farm, Houtpoort (-26.56, 28.37). **Limpopo:** Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); University of Limpopo, Sovenga Hill (-23.88, 29.73); Lhuvhondo Nature reserve (-23.038, 29.442); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Potgietersrus/Mokopane (-24.17, 29.00). **Mpumalanga:** Carolina (-26.06, 30.11); Verloren Vallei Nature Reserve (-25.53, 30.13). **Western Cape:** Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Rondeberg 567 (-33.24, 18.16); Gans Kop 136 (-33.39, 21.01); Melkhoutfontein 480 (-34.19, 21.23).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Protected in >10 protected areas. More sampling needed to collect the female.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the male.

Palp after Lessert (1943)

Philodromus grosi undescribed female from Irene
Photo Peter Webb

Philodromus guineensis Millot, 1941

COMMON NAME: Guinea Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1941 from Guinea. Known from three African countries. In South Africa recorded from six provinces including >10 protected areas (EOO= 52 5148 km²; AOO= 84 km²; 14-1816 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide African range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: They are free-living plant dwellers sampled from vegetation from the Fynbos, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord et al 2011; Haddad et al. 2013) as well as from avocado and citrus orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Guinea, Ivory Coast, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Clocolan, Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92; 27.58); Fouriesburg (-28.61, 28.23). **Gauteng:** Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.80, 28.77); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19); Heidelberg (-26.5, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park: False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27); Hell's Gate (-28.01, 32.48). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Leggalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16). **Mpumalanga:** Brondal, De Villiers 20 km NE (-25.35, 30.84); Burgers Hall (-25.02, 31.08); Glenwood, 7 km NW (-25.48, 30.92); Nelspruit (-25.47; 30.96); Nelspruit, Hall & Sons, 10 km NE (-25.47, 30.96); Lowveld National Botanical Garden (-25.47, 31.00); Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); De Hoop Nature Reserve, Koppie Alleen cottage (-34.286, 20.286).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Protected in >10 protected areas such as Blouberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2019) and Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Philodromus guineensis female Photo Johan van Zyl

Philodromus guineensis female Photo Peter Webb

Palp and epigynum after Millot (1941)

Habitus after Millot (1941)

Philodromus guineensis female from Fouriesburg Photo Peter Webb

Philodromus partitus Lessert, 1919

COMMON NAME: Long Bodied Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1919 from Tanzania. Known from three African countries. Also sampled from four provinces in South Africa including five protected areas (EEO= 245 849 km²; AOO= 36 km²; 30-1299 m a.s.l.). This species is under collected and suspected to occur in the countries in between. Due to the wide range it is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free-living plant dwellers sampled from grasses in the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Tanzania, Zimbabwe, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Coffee Bay (-31.97, 29.14); Cwebe Nature Reserve v(-32.28, 28.9); Kei River Mouth (-32.68, 28.37); Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.9). **Gauteng:** Tswaing Nature Reserve, (-25.41, 28.08). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve, Crocodile Farm (-26.87, 32.24). **Limpopo:** University of Limpopo, Sovenga Hill (-23.88, 29.73); Vhembe Biosphere Ben Lavin Nature Reserve (-23.133, 29.926); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.17, 30.25); Potgietersrus/Mokopane (-24.17, 29.00).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Protected in five protected areas. More sampling needed to collect male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from female.

Habitus after Lessert (1919)

Epigynum after Lessert (1919)

Philodromus partitus female from Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Photo Peter Webb

***Philodromus thanatellus* Strand, 1909**

COMMON NAME: Cape Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described in 1909 and known from juvenile specimen sampled prior to 1909 from the type locality Simonstown (EOO= 4 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 125 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect adult material and to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: Free-living plant dweller sampled from the Fynbos Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Simonstown (Shooting range) (-34.19, 18.42).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Last sampled in 1909, more sampling needed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from a juvenile.

***Philodromus vulpio* Simon, 1910**

COMMON NAME: Namakwa Ground Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described in 1910 and known only from the type sampled in Little Namaqualand. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: They are free-living plant dwellers sampled from vegetation in the Succulent Karoo Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa [in World Catalog erroneously listed as Namibia]

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape*: type only as Little Namaqualand.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female

GENUS *SUEMUS* Simon 1895

Suemus is represented by five species known from Africa and Vietnam. Three species known from the Afrotropical Region and one is known from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: Spotted Suemus philodromid

TYPE SPECIES: *Suemus atomarius* Simon, 1895

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: female 5–7 mm; male smaller and more slender than female. A small group of spiders recognised by their flattened carapace, eye pattern and elongated abdomen. The body is covered with small spots. The front legs are longer than the rest. Colour of body and legs varying from cream to brown or bright orange, with numerous dark spots. Carapace oval, clypeus narrow; integument clothed with setae; eyes: eight in two rows (4:4) with the posterior eye row very strongly recurved and the posterior lateral eyes away from the rest of the eyes; abdomen elongate-oval; legs long and slender, distal segments of anterior legs of male black.

LIFESTYLE: The spotted philodromids are free-living plant dwellers. They are generally found on grasses and occasionally on shrubs.

TAXONOMY: Not revised.

Suemus punctatus male from Hammanskraal Photos Vida van der Walt

Suemus punctatus Lawrence, 1938

COMMON NAME: Spotted Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African spider described by Lawrence (1938) from Pietermaritzburg in KwaZulu-Natal. The species has been recorded from Mozambique, Swaziland and six provinces in South Africa (EOO= 880 923 km²; AOO= 136 km²; 0-1438 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: They are free-living plant dwellers sampled with sweep nets from vegetation and have been sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Forest, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, Swaziland, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Bronkhorstspruit (Farm Onverwacht) (-25.8, 28.74); Groenkloof Nature Reserve (-25.78, 28.20); Hammanskraal (-25.41, 28.27). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Dukudu-ku Forest Station (-28.37; 32.23); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1); Umhlali (-29.47, 31.22). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Kruger National Park: Shingwedzi (20km SE) (-22.93, 31.02); Pafuri (-22.46, 31.3); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Pafuri (Waller's Camp) (-22.42, 30.91); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); University of Limpopo, Sovenga Hill, (-24.17, 29); Roedtan (-24.6, 29.08); Springbok Flats (Tuinplaas) (-24.9, 28.73). **Mpumalanga:** Burgers Hall (-25.02, 31.08); Kruger National Park (-24.98, 31.58); Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-25, 31.97); Kruger National Park, Mopani, Tsendze (-23.691, 31.518); Lapalala Wilderness Game Reserve (-23.84, 28.26); Burgers Hall (-25.02, 31.08); Graskop, 30 km N (-24.93, 30.84); Kruger National Park Lwakahle 08 (-25.43, 31.75); Kruger National Park, Vutomi 09 (-24.61, 31.79). **Northern Cape:** Eselsfontein Farm, S of Grootdrink (-28.62, 21.68); Hoptown (Suffolk Farm) (-29.58, 24.24). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Gouritsmond (Borrefontein) (-34.34, 21.87); Fernkloof Nature Reserve (-34.61, 19.34); Robben Island (-33.8076, 18.3712); Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Protected in eight protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Suemus punctatus female Photo ASD

Abdomen and palp after Lawrence (1938)

Epigynum after Lawrence (1938)

Female from Nelspruit Photo Aart Louw

Suemus punctatus male Photos Vida van der Walt

GENUS *THANATUS* C. L. Koch, 1837

Thanatus is represented by 96 species and three subspecies (World Spider Catalog 2021). Seventeen species are known from the Afrotropical Region and seven are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: Thanatus Running Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Thanatus formicinus* (Clerck, 1757)

MORPHOLOGY: Both sexes medium-sized. *Thanatus* are oval to slightly elongated spiders, the least flattened philodromid spiders. Colour cryptic, creamish-brown with darker patterns; legs frequently banded. Carapace slightly flattened, as wide as it is long; suboval in outline; thoracic region evenly rounded, sloping gently towards cephalic region; fovea usually distinct; integument covered with short setae; eyes eight; small; in two rows; both rows recurved. Abdomen has a distinct dark heart mark. The male is only slightly smaller than the female.

LIFESTYLE: They are found on bare ground or in low vegetation and are commonly collected with a sweepnet from grass or pitfall traps. They prey on a variety of insects including the hoppers of the African migratory locust.

TAXONOMY: African species not revised.

Thanatus sp. eye pattern

Thanatus sp. dorsal view Photo Peter Webb

Thanatus dorsilineatus from Graskop Photo Webb

***Thanatus africanus* Karsch, 1878**

COMMON NAME: African Ground Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described in 1878 from Tanzania (Zanzibar). It was also sampled in South Africa from the Limpopo Province (E00= 8 km²; A00= 16 km²; 182-1431 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Sampled from grass in the Savanna Biome (Foord et al 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Tanzania (Zanzibar), South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Nylsvley Nature Reserve

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Protected in the Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Thanatus atlanticus Berland, 1936

COMMON NAME: Ground Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described in 1936 from the Cape Verde Island. It was also sampled in South Africa from four provinces including three protected areas (EOO= 216 328 km²; AOO= 16 km²; 182-1431 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Sampled from grass in the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Cape Verde Island and South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Ezemvelo Nature reserve (-25.80, 28.77). **Free State:** Ventersburg (-28.08, 27.14). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park, Pafuri (-22.93, 31.02). **Northern Cape:** Namaqua National Park (-30.05, 17.35).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Protected in three protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Habitus and epigynum after Berland (1936)

Thanatus atlanticus from Namaqua National Park Photo ASD

Thanatus dorsilineatus Jézéquel, 1964

COMMON NAME: Striped Legged Ground Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1964 from the Ivory Coast. It is known from three African countries. In South Africa known from seven provinces and >10 protected areas (EOO= 319 142km²; AOO= 72 km²; 1-1909 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: They are free-living plant dwellers sampled with sweep nets from the Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord et al 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). Also sampled from maize fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Ivory Coast, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97). **Free State:** Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.8, 27.65). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23); Irene Veld field opposite Gem Village (-25.89, 28.23); Kliprivier Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland park: Hellsgate (-28, 32.48); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Roedtan (-24.6, 29.08); Springbok Flats: Tuinplaas (-24.9, 28.73); Lekgalameetse Nature reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Vyeboom (-23.144, 30.380). **Mpumalanga:** Delmas (FarmRietvallei) (-26.08, 28.57); Verloren Vallei Nature Reserve (-25.53, 30.13); Wakkerstroom (-27.33, 30.14). **North West:** Kgaswane Nature Reserve (-25.65, 27.22).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Protected in 11 protected areas such as Blouberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2019), Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2011) and Lekgalameetse Nature reserve (Foord et al. 2016).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Epigynum after Jézéquel (1964)

Palp after Jézéquel (1964)

Thanatus dorsilineatus female from Graskop Photo Peter Webb

Thanatus fabricii (Audouin, 1826)

COMMON NAME: Fabrici's Ground Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species with a wide distribution described by Audouin (1826) as *Philodromus fabricii*. It is known from the Canary Island to Central Asia and Africa. Also recorded from South Africa from two provinces (EEO=8 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 1246-1328 m a.s.l.) Due to wide geographical range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Collected with sweep nets from the Savanna Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Canary Is. to Central Asia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Mkhomazi State Forest, Ibya Camp (-29.62, 29.75). *Mpumalanga*: Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Species with a wide distribution. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Thanatus fabricii female from Mariepskop Photo ASD

B.
Palp after Millot (1942)

Epigynum after Millot (1942)

Thanatus lamottei Jézéquel, 1964

COMMON NAME: Lamotte's Ground Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1964 from the Ivory Coast. It was also recorded from South Africa from two provinces from two protected areas: Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve and Ben Lavin Nature Reserve (EOO= 8 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 50-898 m a.s.l.). Due to wide range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Collected with sweep nets from the Fynbos and Savanna biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Ivory Coast, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Limpopo:** Vhembe Biosphere Ben Lavin Nature Reserve (-23.133, 29.926). **Western Cape:** Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve (-34.32, 18.96).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Species with a wide distribution. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Palp after Jézéquel (1964)

Thanatus lamottei female from Ben Lavin Photo ASD

Epigynum after Jézéquel (1964)

Epigynum Photo ASD

Thanatus namaquensis Simon, 1910

COMMON NAME: Namaque Ground Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described in 1910 from Kamaggas. The species only known from the type locality (EOO=4 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 231 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: They are free-living ground dwellers sampled from the Succulent Karoo Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.4); Askam (-26.98, 20.79).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed to collect male and determine species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from the female, not illustrated.

Thanatus namaquensis female from Askam Photo Peter Webb

Thanatus vulgaris Simon, 1870

COMMON NAME: Common Ground Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described in 1870 that has a very wide distribution. In South Africa known from eight of the provinces including >10 protected areas. (EOO= 694 688 km²; AOO= 176 km²; 7-1795 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Introduced species. A common free-living ground and plant dweller sampled in pitfall traps. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). The species also sampled from agro-ecosystems such as cotton, lucerne, maize, potatoes and strawberries (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: North America, North Africa, European to Far East, Central Asia. South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91). **Free State:** Bothaville, Kromvlei, Rusthoek (-27.38, 26.62); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.8, 27.65); Vrede (-27.43, 29.13); Wesselsbron (Kaalplaas) (-27.84, 26.38); Florisbad (-28.46, 26.05); Krugersdrif Dam (-28.53, 25.55); Rusfontein Dam 2060 (-29.15, 26.35); Waterford 99 (-29.43, 26.57); Lissabon (-28.12, 27.24); Bloemfontein (-29.08, 26.10); Naval Hill (-29.06, 26.14); Koppiesdam Nat Reserve (-27.13, 27.42); Boschrand 208 (-29.56, 24.48); Lions Rest (-27.32, 28.32); Sandveld Nat Reserve (-27.40, 25.41); Kalkfontein dam (-29.31, 25.16); Tussen die Riviere Nat Reserve (-30.30, 26.08); Bloemfontein Botanical Gardens (-29.03, 26.13); Willem Pretorius Nat Reserve (-28.17, 27.12); Vaal Dam, near Oranjeville (-26.30, 28.14); Amanzi Nature Reserve (-28.62, 26.68). **Gauteng:** Irene Veld field opposite Gem Village (-25.89, 28.23); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.80, 28.77); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08P). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-23.12, 29.00). **Mpumalanga:** Delmas (Farm Rietvallei) (26.08, 28.57); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29); Wakkerstroom (-27.33, 30.14). Sterkspruit (-25.07, 30.34). **Northern Cape:** Loxton (-31.47, 22.35); Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82). **North West:** Potchefstroom ARC exp. Farm (-26.7, 27.09); Thabela Thabeng Mountain Retreat (-26.52, 27.18).

Thanatus vulgaris female Photo Koos Geldenhuys

Thanatus vulgaris female Photo Peter Webb

Epigynum after Levy (1977)

Palp after Levy (1977)

Thanatus vulgaris (continued)

Western Cape: Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Cape Flats (-34.02, 18.6); Hermanus (-34.40, 19.25); Lemoenshoek (-33.51, 20.51); Olifants Kraal 61 (-32.51, 18.09)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species Protected in several protected areas such as Blouberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2019) and Amanzi Nature Reserve (Haddad & Butler 2018). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Thanatus vulgaris female Photo Les Oates

GENUS *TIBELLUS* Simon, 1875

Tibellus is represented by 49 species and two subspecies (World Spider Catalog 2021). Seventeen species are known from the Afrotropical Region and 13 from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: *Tibellus* Grass Running Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Tibellus oblongus* (Walckenaer, 1802).

MORPHOLOGY: Body size with female and male small to medium-sized. Colour varies from white to pale cream, with reddish brown to creamish-brown bands. Carapace elongated, narrow anteriorly. Their small eyes are grouped closely anteriorly and posterior the eye row is strongly recurved. The posterior median eyes are distinctly closer to each other than to the posterior lateral eyes. Abdomen elongate and covered with soft, recumbent setae, usually with dark heart-shaped mark dorsally. Legs directed sideways; legs I, III and IV similar in length; leg II usually longer.

LIFESTYLE: Small grass-running spiders are free-living plant dwellers commonly found on grass. Their elongated, straw-coloured bodies with dark, longitudinal lines render them inconspicuous on dry grass. Their movements are erratic, but their claw tufts and scopulae enable them to move swiftly on the substrate. They are quick and agile when pursuing their prey. The egg-sacs are attached to grass tufts, and are guarded by the female. They prey on a variety of insects that live on grass.

TAXONOMY: Genus revised by Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994).

Tibellus minor

Tibellus hollidayi

Tibellus gerhardi

Tibellus sp. on egg sac at Mpetsane Photo Allen Jones

Tibellus armatus Lessert, 1928

COMMON NAME: Central Africa Grass Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1928 from the Democratic Republic of the Congo and it is known from six African countries. In South Africa known from KwaZulu-Natal and Free State (EOO= 16 523 km²; AOO= 16 km²; 27-1593 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free living plant dwellers. They are commonly found on bushes and tall grass. Sampled from Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord et al 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Mozambique, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Free State:* Clocolan, Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58). *KwaZulu-Natal:* Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-29.473, 29.893); Midlands, Wakefield Farm (-28.78, 32.1).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Species with a wide distribution. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Van den Berg and Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994). Known from both sexes, illustrated.

Palp after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994).

Epigynum after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994).

Tibellus armatus female on egg sac at Mpetsane Photo Allen Jones

Tibellus australis (Simon, 1910)

COMMON NAME: Botswana Grass Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1910 from Botswana. Known from three African countries. In South Africa known from Limpopo and protected in the Blouberg Nature Reserve (EEO= 8 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 894-1372 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free living plant dwellers. They are commonly found on bushes and tall grass from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Zimbabwe, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Species with a wide distribution. Blouberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2019) No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Van den Berg and Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994). Known only from female, illustrated.

Tibellus australis Photo P. Webb

Habitus after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994).

Epigynum after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994).

Tibellus bruneitarsis Lawrence, 1952

COMMON NAME: Umhahli Grass Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1952 from Umhahli in KwaZulu-Natal. The species is known from two African countries. In South Africa known from Limpopo and KwaZulu-Natal and it is protected in the Polokwane Nature Reserve (EOO= 44 574 km²; AOO= 16 km²; 18-1310 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free living plant dwellers. They are commonly found on bushes and tall grass in the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Mtunzini Twin Streams Farm (-28.96, 31.76); Umhahli (-29.47, 31.22). *Limpopo:* Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Species with a wide distribution. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Van den Berg and Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994). Known only from female.

Epigynum after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994).

Tibellus bruneitarsis female Photo ASD

***Tibellus cobusi* Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994**

COMMON NAME: Cobus's Grass Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1994 from Potgietersrus in the Limpopo. The species is sampled from three African countries. In South Africa known only from Limpopo and protected in the Blouberg Nature Reserve and Malebogo Nature Reserve (EOO= 1 098 km²; AOO= 12 km²; 894-1261 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and therefore can be listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free living plant dwellers. They are commonly found on bushes and tall grass and sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, Somalia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Malebogo Nature Reserve, nr. Blouberg (-23.07, 28.88); Potgietersrus/Mokopane, Sterk River Dam (-24.17, 29).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Blouberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2019) Species with a wide distribution. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from male.

Palp after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994).

***Tibellus demangei* Jézéquel, 1964**

COMMON NAME: Ivory Coast Grass Running Spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1964 from the Ivory Coast. This species is under collected and suspected to occur in more intervening countries. In South Africa, the species is recorded from KwaZulu-Natal (EOO= 4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 78 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free living plant dwellers. They are commonly found on bushes and tall grass sampled from the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Ivory Coast, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Species with a wide distribution. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Van den Berg and Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994). Known from both sexes

Palp after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994).

Epigynum after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994).

Tibellus flavipes Caporiacco, 1939

COMMON NAME: Zululand Grass Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1939 from Kenya. Known from five African countries. In South Africa known only from KwaZulu-Natal including six protected areas (EOO=8 888 km²; AOO= 40 km²; 18-150 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free living plant dwellers. They are commonly found on bushes and tall grass in the Savanna and Indian Ocean Coastal Belt biomes (Foord et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Kenya, Mozambique, Somalia, Tanzania, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Enseleni Nature Reserve (-28.68, 32.05); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Mkuze between Mkuze and Jozini (through Lebombo Mountain) (-27.6, 32.02); Mkuze, 20 km S (-27.6, 32.02); Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Jozini, between Jozini and Ndumu (-27.42, 32.07); Jozini between Jozini, Mkuze and Lebombo Mnts. (-27.42, 32.07); Mtubatuba, 20 km N on Nongoma Road (-28.4, 32.18); Mtunzini (-28.96, 31.76); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Nyala Game Reserve (-28.72, 31.88).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Species with a wide distribution. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Van den Berg and Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994). Known from both sexes

Tibellus flavipes from Mkuze Photo Les Oates

Palp and abdomen after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-

Epigynum after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994).

Tibellus gerhardi Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994

COMMON NAME: Loskopdam Grass Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1994 from Loskopdam in Mpumalanga. The species is known from seven African countries. In South Africa known from five provinces including four protected areas. (EOO= 86 154 km²; AOO= 40 km²; 91-1698 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free-living plant dwellers. They are commonly found on bushes and tall grass in Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Mozambique, Sudan, Zimbabwe, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Acornhoek (-24.58, 31.1); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47). **Mpumalanga:** Groblersdal (-25.16, 29.39); Kaapmuiden (-25.54, 31.33); Loskop Dam (-25.46, 29.23); Carolina (-26.06, 30.11). **North West:** Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Species with a wide distribution. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Tibellus gerhardi female on egg sac from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Palp after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994).

Epigynum after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994)

Habitus after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994)

Tibellus gerhardi female from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Tibellus hollidayi Lawrence, 1952

COMMON NAME: Pietermaritzburg Grass Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1952 from Pietermaritzburg in KwaZulu-Natal. The species is known from six African countries. In South Africa known from eight provinces including >10 protected areas (EOO= 584 416 km²; AOO= 184 km²; 47-1919 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free living plant dwellers. They are commonly found on bushes and tall grass. Sampled from Fynbos, Grassland, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord et al 2011; Had-dad et al. 2013)

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Ethiopia, Rwanda, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** 32 km from Aliwal North on Lady Grey road (-30.69, 26.71); Lady Grey (-30.71, 27.2). **Free State:** Aasvoelberg (-30.3, 27.05); Bainsvlei Tempe Research Farm (-29.02, 26.17); Farm Hopefield (-28.9, 26.23); Farm Deel-hoek (-30.98, 23.81); Rosthof (-29.11, 26.22); Clarens (Farm Adullum) (-28.51, 28.43); Clocolan, Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Ficksburg, Sentra-Oos Nature Reserve (-28.86, 27.86); Kestell (-28.35, 28.72); Oran-jeville (-26.99, 28.2); Rustfontein (-29.82, 26.43); Tussen die Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.47, 25.19); Winburg (-28.49, 27); Wurasoord (-44.6, 26); Ventersburg (-28.08, 27.14); Phi-landspan 857 (-28.48, 26.03); Qwa Qwa Nature Reserve, Eerstegeluk 131 (-28.26, 28.41); De Brug (-29.08, 25.57); Florisbad (-28.46, 26.05); Bloemfontein Botanical Gardens (-29.08, 26.10). **Gauteng:** Bronkhorstspuit (Farm Onverwacht) (-25.8, 28.74); Irene (Smuts House) (-25.89, 28.23); Johannesburg, Four Ways Golf Course (-26.2, 28.04); Johannesburg, Naturena (-26.2, 28.04); Kemptonpark (Esther Park) (-26.1, 28.2); Lochvaal, North Shore (-26.73, 27.68); Melville Koppies (-26.17, 27.99); Midrand (-25.95, 28.14); Nigel (-26.42, 28.46); Norscott Nature Reserve (-26.2, 28.04); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-27.59, 27.53); Van Riebeeck Nature Reserve (-25.85, 28.16). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24). **Limpopo:** Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Potgietersrus/Mokopane (-24.17, 29); Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63) Lekgal-ameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16).

Tibellus hollidayi female from Mpetsane
Photo Allen Jones

Epigynum after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994).

Palp after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994).

Tibellus hollidayi Photo Allen Jones

Tibellus hollidayi (continued)

Mpumalanga: Bourke's Luck (-25.09, 30.46). **North West:** Broederstroom (Farm Brooklands) (-25.78, 27.87); Klerksdorp, Rd. between Klerksdorp and Wolmaranstad (-26.84, 26.67); Pilanesberg Nature Reserve (-25.25, 27.08); Potchefstroom Experiment Station (-26.68, 27.12); (-26.7, 27.09); Skeerpoort (-25.81, 27.75). **Western Cape:** Hopefield (-33.06, 18.36); Swartklip (-34.19, 18.42).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. It is protected in >10 protected areas). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Van den Berg and Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994). Known from both sexes.

Tibellus hollidayi female Irene Photo Peter Webb

Tibellus hollidayi female Irene Photo Peter Webb

Tibellus kibonotensis Lessert, 1919

COMMON NAME: Tanzania Grass Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1919 from Tanzania. The species has been sampled from several African countries. In South Africa known from four provinces and protected in the Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (EOO= 50 887 km²; AOO= 24km²; 18-1722 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free living plant dwellers. They are commonly found on bushes and tall grass sampled from the Grassland, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Burkina Faso, East Africa, Malawi, Mozambique, Rwanda, Tanzania, Uganda, Zimbabwe, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Krugersdorp/Mogale, Elandslaagte (-26.09, 27.78); between Pretoria and Bronkhortspruit (-25.74, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Mtunzini (-28.96, 31.76). **Limpopo:** Zwartwater 161(-27.05,30.51). **Mpumalanga:** Kendal (Farm Heuwelfontein) (-26.07, 28.99).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Species with a wide distribution. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Van den Berg and Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994). Known from both sexes.

Tibellus kibonotensis Photo P. Webb

Palp, epigynum and habitus after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994)

Tibellus minor Lessert, 1919

COMMON NAME: Common Grass Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1919 from Tanzania. The species is known from several African countries. In South Africa known from eight provinces including >10 protected areas (EOO= 991 261 km²; AOO= 304 km²; 7-2020 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free living plant dwellers. They are commonly found on bushes and tall grass from Fynbos, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Nama Karoo, Savanna, Succulent Karoo and Thicket biomes (Foord et al 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). Also sampled from crops such as cotton, maize and vineyards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Wide throughout Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Baroe (-33.21, 24.58); East London (-33.01, 27.9); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Mpofu Nature Reserve (32.61, 26.60); Patensie, Otterford Forest Station (-33.76, 24.81); Port Alfred Road between Port Alfred and East London (-33.58, 26.89). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Bloemfontein (Farm Deelhoek) (-29.11, 26.22); Clocolan, Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Ficksburg (-28.86, 27.86); Florisbad Research Station (-28.77, 26.07); Golden Gate Nature Reserve (-28.5, 28.62); Tussen die Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.47, 25.19); Vrede (-27.43, 29.13). **Gauteng:** Centurion (-25.85, 28.16); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Johannesburg, Leondale (-26.2, 28.04); Krugersdorp/Mogale, Elandsplaagte (-26.09, 27.78); Melville Koppies (-26.17, 27.99); Norscott Nature Reserve (-26.2, 28.04); Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Roodepoort, Lindhaven (-26.14, 27.86); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-27.59, 27.53); Wonderboom Nature Reserve (-25.69, 28.19). Irene Smuts House (-25.89, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Makatini Flats on the road to Sodwana (-27.25, 32.22); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Thanda Private Game Reserve, 23 km N of Hluhluwe (-27.87, 32.13); Westville (-29.82, 30.92).

Palp after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994)

Epigynum after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994)

Tibellus minor female from Lephahlale Photo Peter Webb

Tibellus minor continued

Limpopo: Bandelierkop (-23.31, 29.79); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Kruger National Park (Shingwedzi Camp) (-22.93, 31.02); Lajuma Mountain Retreat (-23.03, 29.45); Limpopo Valley Nature Reserve (-22.22, 29.13); Lephahlale, farm Zandrivier (-23.48, 27.46); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Springbok Flats: Tuinplaas (-24.9, 28.73); Strydom Tunnel (-24.4, 30.61); Vaalwater (-24.29, 28.11). **Mpumalanga:** Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29); Ohrigstad (-24.74, 30.58); Oudestad Research Station (-25.16, 29.39). **North West:** Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58); Borakalalo Game Reserve (-25.14, 27.82); Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Pilanesberg Nature Reserve (-25.25, 27.08); Potchefstroom, ARC Exp. Farm (-26.7, 27.09); Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Western Cape:** Cape Town, Goodwood (-33.91, 18.42); Table Mountain National Park (Lions Head) (-33.91, 18.42); Ceres, 40 km NE on Touws River Road (-33.36, 19.31); Clanwilliam (-32.16, 18.89); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Jacobsbaai, Saldanha Bay district (-33.15, 18.03); Kommetjie (-34.16, 18.34); Malmesbury, Rondeberg 567 (-33.46, 18.74); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Swartklip (-34.19, 18.42); Groot Fontein 105 (-32.04, 18.39); Kookfontein 88 (-32.07, 18.25); Rooielsberg (-34.25, 18.58).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Protected in More than 10 protected areas. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Van den Berg and Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994). Known from both sexes.

Tibellus minor female from Lephahlale Photo Peter Webb

Tibellus seriepunctatus Simon, 1907

COMMON NAME: Spotted Grass Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1907 from Sierra Leone. Known from several African countries. In South Africa known from two provinces and protected in the Mkambati Nature Reserve (EOO= 8 km²; AOO=8 km²; 1-1415 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range therefore listed as of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free living plant dwellers. They are commonly found on bushes and tall grass sampled from the Grassland, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al 2011; Haddad et al. 2013)

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Wide throughout Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97). *Mpumalanga:* Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Dullstroom (-25.42, 30.10).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Species with a wide distribution. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Van den Berg and Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994). Known from both sexes.

Tibellus seriepunctatus from Dullstroom
Photo Peter Webb

Palp, epigynum and habitus after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994)

Tibellus seriepunctatus juvenile Photo Peter Webb

Tibellus sunetae Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994

COMMON NAME: Sunet's Grass Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1994 from Ndumo Game Reserve in KwaZulu-Natal. The species is known from three African countries. In South Africa known from three provinces including four protected areas (EOO= 40 618 km²; AOO= 16 km²; 47-1412 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free living plant dwellers. They are commonly found on bushes and tall grass in the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, Zimbabwe, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). *Limpopo:* Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45). *Mpumalanga:*

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Species with a wide distribution. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Tibellus sunetae. Photo Les Oates

Palp, epigynum and habitus after Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994)

***Tibellus vossioni* Simon, 1884**

COMMON NAME: African Grass Running Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1884 from Sudan. Known from several African countries. In South Africa known from two provinces and protected in the Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve. (EOO= 8 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 7-1247 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free living plant dwellers. They are found on bushes and tall grass from the Fynbos and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Egypt, Ethiopia, Ivory Coast, Sudan, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **Western Cape:** Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Species with a wide distribution. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Van den Berg and Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994). Only known from only male.

Palp after Van den Berg
& Dippenaar-Schoeman (1994)

UNDETERMINED SPECIES

NEW GENUS P. Webb

Kwamalanga P. Webb

Irene P. Webb

Tswaing P. Webb

Irene P. Webb

Hermannsburg P. Webb

Wyndford P. Webb

Hoedspruit P. Webb

Aardvark P. Webb

Irene P. Webb

Irene P. Webb

REFERENCES

- AUDOUIN, V. 1826. Explication sommaire des planches d'arachnides de l'Egypte et de la Syrie publiées ... in "Description de l'Egypte...". *Histoire Naturelle* 14: 1-339 arachnids, pp. 99-186.
- BRIGNOLI, P. M. 1983. *A Catalog of the Araneae described between 1940 and 1981*. Manchester University Press, 755 pp.
- CAPORIACCO, L. DI 1939. Arachnida. In: Missione biologica nel paese dei Borana. Raccolte zoologiche. *Reale Accademia d'Italia, Roma* 3, 303-385.
- CAPORIACCO, L. DI 1941. Arachnida esc. Acarina. *Missione Biologica Sagan-Omo, Reale Accademia d'Italia, Roma Zool.* 6: 1-159.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2014. *Field Guide of the Spiders of South Africa*. Lapa Publisher 424 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & JOCQUÉ, R. 1997. *African spiders, an identification manual*. Biosystematics Division, ARC-Plant Protection Research Institute, Pretoria. Handbook 9, 392.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & VAN DEN BERG, A.M. 2010. *Spiders of the Kalahari*. Plant Protection Handbook no 18, Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria, 120 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., FOORD S.H. & HADDAD C.R. 2013. *Spiders of the Savanna Biome*. University of Venda & Agricultural Research Council.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & HADDAD C.R. 2014. *Spiders of the Grassland Biome*. Plant Protection Handbook no 19, Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria, 120 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., HADDAD, C.R., FOORD, S.H., LYLE, R., LOTZ, L.N., HELBERG, L., MATHEBULA, S., VAN DEN BERG, A., VAN DEN BERG, A.M., VAN NIEKERK, E. AND JOCQUÉ, R. 2010. First Atlas of the Spiders of South Africa. South African National Survey of Arachnida. *SANSA Technical Report version 1 (2010)*: 1158 pp.
- HOLM, E. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2010. *Goggo Guide*. Lapa Publisher 304 pp.
- JÉZÉQUEL, J.-F. 1964. Araignées de la savane de Singrobo Côte d'Ivoire. III.-Thomisidae. *Bulletin de l'Institut Fondamental d'Afrique Noire* 26A: 1103-1143.
- JÉZÉQUEL, J.-F. 1966. Araignées de la savane de Singrobo (Côte d'Ivoire). V.-Note complémentaire sur les Thomisidae. *Bulletin du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle de Paris* 37: 613-630.
- JOCQUÉ R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., 2006. *Spider families of the World*. Royal Museum for Central Africa. 334 pp.
- LAWRENCE, R. F. 1927. Contributions to a knowledge of the fauna of South-West Africa V. Arachnida. *Annals of the South African Museum* 251: 1-525.
- LAWRENCE, R. F. 1938. A collection of spiders from Natal and Zululand. *Annals of the Natal Museum* 8: 455-524.
- LAWRENCE, R. F. 1942. A contribution to the araneid fauna of Natal and Zululand. *Annals of the Natal Museum* 10: 141-190.
- LAWRENCE, R. F. 1952. New spiders from the eastern half of South Africa. *Annals of the Natal Museum* 12: 183-226.
- LESSERT, R. DE 1919. Araignées du Kilimandjaro et du Merou suite. 3. Thomisidae. *Revue Suisse de Zoologie* 27: 99-234.
- LESSERT, R. DE 1928. Araignées du Congo recueillies au cours de l'expédition par l'American Museum 1909-1915. Deuxième partie. *Revue Suisse de Zoologie* 35: 303-352.
- LESSERT, R. DE 1933. Araignées d'Angola. Resultats de la Mission scientifique suisse en Angola 1928-1929. *Revue Suisse de Zoologie* 404: 85-159.
- LESSERT, R. DE 1943. Araignées du Congo Belg III. *Revue Suisse de Zoologie* 50: 305-338.
- LEVY, G. 1977. The philodromid spiders of Israel (Araneae: Philodromidae). *Israel Journal of Zoology* 26: 193-229.
- LYAKHOV, O. V. 2000. Contribution to the Middle Asian fauna of the spider genus *Thanatus* C. L. Koch, 1837 Aranei: Philodromidae. *Arthropoda Selecta* 8: 221-230.

REFERENCES

- MILLOT, J. 1942. Les araignées de l'Afrique Occidentale Français: Thomisidae. *Mémoires de l'Académie des Sciences de Paris* 2 65: 1-82.
- PICKARD-CAMBRIDGE, O. 1876. Catalogue of a collection of spiders made in Egypt, with descriptions of new species and characters of a new genus. *Proceedings of the Zoological Society of London* 1876: 541-630.
- SIMON, E. 1870. Aranéides nouveaux ou peu connus du midi de l'Europe. *Mémoires de la Société Royale des Sciences de Liège* 2 3: 271-358.
- SIMON, E. 1884. Arachnides recueillis à Khartoum Soudan égyptien par M. Vossion, vice-consul de France et appartenant au Muséum de Paris. *Bulletin de la Société Zoologique de France* 9: 1-28.
- SIMON, E. 1895. Descriptions d'arachnides nouveaux de la famille des Thomisidae. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* 39: 432-443.
- SIMON, E. 1907. Arachnides recueillis en Egypte et le long du Nil Blanc par la Mission zoologique suédoise, 1901. In: Results of the Swedish Zoological Expedition to Egypt and the White Nile 1901 under the Direction of L. A. Jägerskiöld. Uppsala 21: 1-10.
- SIMON, E. 1910. Arachnoidea. Araneae ii. In: Schultze, L. ed. Zoologische und anthropologische Ergebnisse einer Forschungsreise im Westlichen und zentralen Südafrika. *Denkschriften der Medizinisch-Naturwissenschaftlichen Gesellschaft zu Jena* 16, 175-218.
- STRAND, E. 1907a. Vorläufige Diagnosen afrikanischer und südamerikanischer Spinnen. *Zoologischer Anzeiger* 31: 525-558.
- STRAND, E. 1907b. Afrikanische Spinnen exkl. Aviculariiden hauptsächlich aus dem Kapland. *Zoologische Jahrbücher, Abteilung für Systematik, Geographie und Biologie der Tiere* 25: 557-731.
- STRAND, E. 1909. Spinnentiere von Südafrika und einigen Inseln gesammelt bei der deutschen Südpolar-Expedition. In: Deutsche Südpolar-Expedition 1901-1905. Berlin 105, 541-596.
- STRAND, E. 1932. Miscellanea nomenklatorica zoologica et palaeontologica, III, IV. *Folia Zoologica et Hydrobiologica, Rigā* 4: 133-147, 193-196.
- VAN DEN BERG, A. AND DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A. S. 1994. A revision of the Afrotropical species of the genus *Tibellus* Simon Araneae: Philodromidae. *Koedoe* 37: 67-114.
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG 2021. World Spider Catalog. Version 21.0. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://WorldSpiderCatalog.nmbe.ch>, accessed on 20 January.